

LESSONS ON MASTERING THE MELODICS OF SPEECH ON EXAMPLES OF VARIOUS TYPES OF SENTENCES

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Abstract: *This article talks about teaching students the correct logical, phrasal accents, correct emotional intonation when reading texts, sentences. About the ability to use conventional signs and terms in Russian literature lessons. Students should be able to raise and lower their voice correctly with punctuation marks. Also of no small importance is the pace of reading sentences.*

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In the process of communication, something is stated, certain motives are asked about or expressed. In accordance with this purpose of speech, there are four most clearly opposed melodies: affirmative (narrative), interrogative, imperative and exclamation. . In school practice, these melodies are assimilated when studying narrative, interrogative and exclamation sentences.

When studying simple sentences for their purpose in speech, special attention is drawn to the motivation of the enclosed utterance, the sound characteristic of the final phrasal link, the dependence of the qualitative characteristics of the intonation elements on the type of sentence. The disclosure of these aspects of different types of sentences and the characteristics of the types of exercises related to the type of sentence will be given further.

It should be noted that the approach to observing the intonation of any type of sentences almost always remains the same, and the newly acquired skills always rely on the skills previously indicated by us. The order of these observations (teachers, students) is approximately as follows:

- 1) the emotional tone of the utterance of the sentence.
- 2) Awareness of thoughts and feelings, expressed sentences.
- 3) Elucidation of the phase links of the proposal.
- 4) Determination of the intonation pattern of each phase link:
 - a) finding phrasal stress;
 - b) establishment of logical stress;
 - c) characteristics of the quality of pauses at the junction of parts of the sentence and especially after the last phrasal link;
 - d) setting the pitch in the pre-impact, percussive and percussive parts of the phrasal link.
- 5) Reading the entire sentence (expressive reading).

When teaching students the correct intonation of a sentence, they should develop self-learning skills, which is created by an attentive attitude to the text, the ability to find means in it that suggest intonation:

- a) author's remarks characterizing the sound of the statement ("... and quietly says: "And how do you know, uncle, that my name is Vanya?" - M. Sholokhov, "The Fate of man";
- b) punctuation marks, the ability to "read" them;
- c) the order of words in a sentence;

d) particles having intonational meaning.

Naturally, all these skills are created taking into account the speech development of students. At the initial stage of training, the teacher himself determines the intonation characteristic of the sentence, gives a sample of its correct reading. Then there is a collective work in this direction, and only then the students independently prepare intonationally expressive reading.

MASTERING THE INTONATION OF A NARRATIVE SENTENCE

Narrative sentences affirm or deny anything about the phenomena of the real world. The nature of affirmation or denial on the part of one's expressiveness can manifest itself in various ways in general education and literary texts. The former are emotionally neutral. It is no coincidence that the syntactic constructions of these articles are characterized by the presence of an absolute advantage of narrative sentences.

From these texts, it is necessary to begin teaching students to consciously familiarize themselves with the nature of the intonation of a narrative sentence in Russian. The initial period of mastering the intonation of sentences of a literary text at first should go in an imitative way.

It is relatively easy to create initial skills of intonation analysis of narrative sentences on general education texts: division into phrasal links, finding logical stress, determining the tone in the initial, middle and final phrasal links.

Children should learn that a narrative sentence is read with a slight calm lowering of the voice to the point, and a calm, unemotional speech, then the last verbal stress increases in the phrasal link: "Autumn has come. The collective farm has a good harvest of grapes." The pitch increase occurs in the non-finite phrasal link, and the decrease occurs in the final sentence phrasal link.

When working with general education articles, students get acquainted with certain terminology: logical stress, tone "increase, decrease", voice strength "volume",

pause; learn to use conditional signs: $\wedge$ - logical stress, $\uparrow$ - tone increase, $\downarrow$ - tone decrease; | and | | - pause.

At the very first lessons of acquaintance with the role of intonation and its means, students should realize:

a) that thanks to intonation, individual words merge into one sentence;

b) what do the terms "intonation", "pause", "tone", "logical stress" mean. (It is desirable that students initially get acquainted with these terms in the lessons of reading native literature).

The goal is achieved something like this:

The teacher points to individual items of the classroom environment, asking: What's it? Students give an answer and write down the words on the blackboard. Teacher: "What did you write? (Words.) Here, words name individual objects. But what have we said about the objects themselves? What message did you make, what thought did you express? (They didn't say anything about the items, we just named them.) That's right, we express our thoughts not in separate words, but in a sentence, a phrase that consists of separate words.

And how to assemble words into separate sentences? Is it possible to make one sentence with the words plane, went, on foot? (No, you can't.) That's right, words that are connected to each other in meaning, in a semantic sense, are combined into a sentence.

Now let's write the following words on the board: we, well, rest, camp. Is it possible to make a sentence with these words? (We had a good rest in the camp.) What did you do with the words rest, camp? (Changed them.) Why? (These words in the sentence are grammatically related to others.) This means that it is necessary to collect words in a sentence according to the laws of grammar, and not only according to the meaning.

Read each word separately in this sentence. What did you do after saying it? (Stop, pause.) That's right, a stop in the voice, in the sound is called a pause. Did you pronounce every word quickly? (No.) And now say the whole sentence (children read

the sentence). Have you noticed that now you didn't have to pause after every word? (Yes.) You said the words faster than before (Yes.) You pronounced the words together, and therefore faster, so you increased the tempo, the speed of pronunciation.

Say the individual words again. Have you noticed that you pronounce every word equally loudly? (Yes.) And now read the whole sentence (children are reading). And now you have pronounced all the words equally loudly? (No.) That's right, you changed the volume, the strength of the voice.

Which word is pronounced louder than others, with more power of voice? The one that is the main one in value. Name this word in our sentence (ok) That's right, this word has a logical emphasis. This means that logical stress highlights the sentence the main word in meaning, the word that emphasizes the main idea of the sentence.

Pauses, tempo, strength of voice, logical stress are the means of intonation. There are others, but you will learn about them later. With the help of intonation, as you can see, the words are linked into one sentence. And so, words are linked into sentences according to their semantic connection, grammatical rules and with the help of intonation."

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